

PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF ONCOLOGICAL PATIENTS

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Abstract. This article scientifically examines the improvement of the psychological state and quality of life in patients with oncological diseases. In addition, the article analyzes the psychological foundations of raising the morale of patients with oncological diseases, increasing their confidence in life and living.

Keywords. Oncological disease, cancer, psychological state, quality of life, psychotherapy.

Introduction.

In recent years, as a result of the rapid development of medicine, the possibilities of early detection and treatment of oncological diseases are expanding. Nevertheless, cancer remains one of the most pressing health problems worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of people are infected with this disease every year, and most of them end up in a serious psycho-psychological state. Cancer negatively affects not only physical health, but also the mental state, emotions, social relationships, and even their hope and motivation for life. Therefore, psychological approaches play an important role in improving the quality of life of oncological patients. A cancer diagnosis is usually a psychological shock for the patient. It evokes negative emotions - fear, hopelessness, depression, anger, denial, and even thoughts of suicide. In this case, it is necessary not only to treat the patient physically, but also to ensure his psychological stability and create spiritual support. Therefore, psychological support and psychotherapy are considered an integral part of oncological care.

The concept of quality of life is broad and multifaceted, and it includes not only the patient's physical condition, but also his mental state, social activity, interpersonal relationships, independence, economic status and level of satisfaction with life. For oncological patients, quality of life is not just survival, but the opportunity to live a full and meaningful life during this period.

The main goal of psychological support is to activate the patient's internal resources, develop stress-fighting skills, increase adaptability to the disease and maintain a positive attitude towards life. Psychological support can be provided in the form of individual conversations, group therapies, family counseling,

conscious mind-management techniques (for example, mindfulness), motivational training and other forms.

Also, the cooperation of medical psychologists, psychiatrists, psychotherapists, social workers and even volunteers plays an important role in improving the psychological condition of oncological patients. By providing psychological support to the patient, their participation in the treatment process, their confidence in the treatment, and their chances of recovery are significantly increased.

Based on the above, this topic - the importance of psychological approaches in improving the quality of life of oncological patients - is not only relevant, but also extremely important from a social and human perspective. By studying this topic in depth, it is possible to contribute to improving the mental state of patients, increasing their quality of life, and creating a more comfortable, supportive environment for them.

Literature analysis and methodology. The famous Canadian psychiatrist and psycho-oncologist Harvey Chochinov conducted a number of scientific studies to improve the quality of life and psychological state of cancer patients. The psychotherapy method developed by him, known as "Dignity Therapy", is based on the written expression of important events and values in the patient's life. This approach helps to maintain the patient's sense of self-esteem and improve his mental state. In addition, Chochinov has also created a special diagnostic tool called the Patient Dignity Inventory (PDI), which is used to assess patients' concerns about their dignity.

Australian scientist Phyllis Batou, a professor at the University of Sydney, specializes in the study of the psychological state of cancer patients and their psychological support. She is one of the founders of the Psycho-Oncology Co-operative Research Group (PoCoG), an organization that works to identify and meet the psychological needs of cancer patients. Batou's research focuses on improving patient-doctor communication, increasing participation in clinical decision-making, and ensuring psychological stability.

Linda Carlson is a clinical psychologist in Canada who has developed effective approaches to reducing stress levels and improving overall quality of life for cancer patients. The psychological programs she has developed, based on mindfulness, help stabilize the patient's mental state. Carlson's research shows that the mindfulness approach has a significant effect on reducing negative emotions and strengthening positive mood in cancer patients.

British psycho-oncologist Leslie Fallowfield has conducted important research on the assessment of the quality of life of cancer patients and the improvement of doctor-patient communication. He has developed special methods for measuring the quality of life and has introduced training programs for medical staff aimed at effective communication with patients. His research substantiates the need to take into account the psychological needs of the patient when providing oncological care.

Professors working at Ohio State University in the USA have studied how psychological support for cancer patients affects their treatment process. In a study conducted in 1999, they supported 115 women with breast cancer with psychological counseling and found that as a result their psychological state and response to treatment significantly improved. This research shows that psychological support also has a positive effect on clinical outcomes.

Discussion. Oncological diseases have a profound impact not only on physical health, but also on a person's mental, social and emotional state. In particular, receiving a cancer diagnosis, the difficult treatment process, and the unexpected consequences of the disease can cause severe stress, anxiety, depression, and even suicidal thoughts in the human psyche. Therefore, it is becoming increasingly clear that in modern medicine, treatment with only pharmacological or surgical methods is not enough. Psychological support is becoming an integral and important part of oncological care.

Psychological foundations are understood as factors such as activating the patient's internal psychological resources, maintaining mental stability, combating stress, restoring hope for life, and increasing self-esteem. Each patient reacts differently to a cancer diagnosis: some are in denial, others are angry, and still others are in despair. From this perspective, an individual approach to each patient is necessary.

Psychotherapeutic approaches include Dignity Therapy, Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction (MBSR), cognitive-behavioral therapy, expressive writing, art therapy, and group counseling. Dignity Therapy, developed by Harvey Chochinov, in particular, helps patients find meaning in their lives, maintain self-esteem, and appreciate their experiences.

Mindfulness-based methods, as proposed by Linda Carlson, also help patients focus on the present moment and get rid of negative thoughts. Studies show that this type of psychological support significantly reduces the level of depression, anxiety, and insomnia in cancer patients.

Social and family support also plays an important role in the psychological state of the patient. Positive attitudes from family members, friends, and society increase the patient's motivation for treatment. On the contrary, loneliness, neglect, and social isolation reduce the quality of life.

In addition, the quality of communication between the patient and the doctor is also important. Studies have shown that active participation of patients in the treatment process and participation in decision-making improves their psychological state and increases the quality of life.

However, in practice, the provision of psychological support faces many problems. In particular, the resources allocated to psychologists in the healthcare system are insufficient, and in many cases, doctors consider psychological care to be secondary or patients cannot use these services. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically introduce and develop psychological care in the healthcare system in the future.

Conclusion. Oncological diseases are a serious condition that deeply affects not only the physical state of a person's health, but also his or her mental and social life. A cancer diagnosis is accompanied by negative emotions such as stress, depression, hopelessness, and loneliness for many patients. Therefore, psychological support, in addition to medical treatment, is a necessary and integral part of the process of fighting cancer.

Studies show that psychological approaches — in particular, Dignity therapy, mindfulness-based stress reduction, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and socio-psychological counseling — play an important role in stabilizing the patient's mental state, restoring self-esteem, and maintaining a positive attitude towards life. Patients who receive psychological support are more involved in the treatment process, establish effective communication with doctors, and have a positive attitude towards treatment.

Also, family and social support, open communication between the patient and the doctor, as well as psychological support based on an individual approach are important factors in improving the overall quality of life of the patient.

On this basis, it can be concluded that organizing psychological support on a systematic and scientific basis when working with oncological patients, supporting them mentally and developing resilience significantly improves their quality of life. Such an approach is one of the important indicators of a healthy society and the provision of quality medical care.

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